

Research Article

Analgesic Activity of *Vigna unguiculata* in CD-1 Mice Following Formalin Administration

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Abstract

This study was intended to determine the effects of Vigna unguiculata on pain sensation in 40 adult Swiss white mice. The mice were randomly selected into four groups (A, B, C and D) and allowed to acclimatize for a period of 3 weeks. With free access to food and water. They were subsequently subjected to a treated period of 4 weeks, during which group B, C and D (test group) received cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diets containing 50% (cooked and uncooked beans) and 0.2/50g serotonin precursor diets. Group A, however (control), received normal rodent chow. The results in the formalin test, shows that the frequency and duration of paw attention in both phases of the test groups was significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) compared to the control group. The duration and frequency of paw licks ($P < 0.05$) was also significantly lower in the beans diet and serotonin precursor group compared to the control. Therefore, chronic consumption of Vigna unguiculata diet may decrease pain sensation.

Keywords: *Vigna unguiculata*, pain, formalin and mice.

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Introduction

Vigna unguiculata (Cowpea) is a legume belonging to the family *fabaceae*. It is the second important pulse crop in Africa, with Nigeria producing nearly 2 million metric tonnes annually (Singh *et al.*, 2002) and is a rich source of protein, carbohydrates, dietary fibre, minerals, vitamins etc (Adeyere, 1995). It has also been reported that beans contain serotonin and its precursor 5-Hydroxytryptophan (5-HTP) (Portas *et al.*, 2000) and other chemical compounds including saponins, tannins, glycosides, flavonoids etc. Among the array of chemical constituents, notably, serotonin has neurobehavioural actions on mood, memory, learning, and sleep (Brunton *et al.*, 2005). This was of particular interest when we consider the challenges that confront human behaviour and how behavioural disorders still remain a global concern (Messman, 2005). Human behaviour is believed to be influenced by endocrine and nervous system. The complexity in the behaviour of an organism is correlated to the complexity of its nervous system. Thus, organism with more complex nervous systems (like human) has a greater capacity to learn new responses and adjust their behaviour. This behaviour is influenced by physical and psychological changes that result from a complex state of feeling described as emotion (Cacioppo and Gardner, 1999). It is likely that behavioural changes can be associated with stable foods like cowpea, since it contains neurotransmitters, especially serotonin and its precursor 5-Hydroxytryptophan, known to exhibit neurobehavioural actions. This study therefore, investigates the effect of cowpea on neurobehavioural parameters using 40 Swiss white mice.

Materials and Methods

Experimental animals:

Forty (40) adult Swiss white mice supplied from Department of Physiology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka were used in this study having weight ranging between 18-29g irrespective of sex. They were housed in labeled cages. The animals were fed with normal rodent chow and tap water. They were allowed to acclimatize for 3 weeks.

Substance preparation: After removal of the outer coverings, the beans were sliced, sun dried and blended into fine powder using electric blender. The fine powdered beans cooked and uncooked was measured using an electric weighing balance. Synthetic serotonin precursor (5-Hydroxytryptophan) was obtained from May and Baker (M&B) limited, Enfield, Middle Sex, United Kingdom (UK), and used for the study. From the

estimation of the powdered 5-Hydroxytryptophan (serotonin precursor) content of beans according to the method of Feldman and M-Lee (1995) as modified by Mosienko *et al.*, (2012). The serotonin precursor diet was prepared by mixing 20mg(0.04g) of the precursor in 100g of the feed. One gram (1g) of the mixture was mixed with 99g of the feed. So that the amount of 5HTP added was equivalent to that contained in the beans diet. An electric blender was used to blend the mixture to form the serotonin precursor diet.

Research Design: The mice were divided into four groups, each containing 10 mice(10) with weight ranging between 18-29g. The four groups were tagged group A,B,C and D were fed in the following orders for 4 weeks.

1. Group A: Normal diet and water only
2. Group B: Normal diet, water and 50% cooked beans
3. Group C: Normal diet, water and uncooked beans
4. Group D: Normal diet, water and 0.2mg/50g 5-HTP.

Procedure: The formalin test was used to assess pain as developed by (Abbott *et al.*, 1981). Each mouse was picked at the base of its tail and 0.2ml of formalin 2.5% concentration was injected into the right hind paw of the mouse using a needle and syringe and placed in the observation box and observed for 5 minutes. The animal was then returned to its cages and allowed for thirty (30) minutes before it was taken back to the observation box to be re-observed for another five (5) minutes. The behaviours' scored were; frequency and duration of paw lick and paw attention.

Data analysis: The data collected during the study were presented as Mean \pm SEM and a "P" value less than 0.001 & 0.05, were regarded as significant. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the student test were used for analysis. Also a post-hoc test (SD) was carried out. Statistical analysis was done with the aid of computer software SPSS Statistical version 15.0 and Excel from windows XP (Brain Series, China).

Results

Frequency of Hind Pain Lick Following Formalin Administration

Figure 1 shows the frequency of right hind paw licks for mice fed normal, cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diets as 14.90 ± 1.59 ; 12.86 ± 1.68 ; 7.71 ± 0.75 and $5.71 \pm 0.42/5$ mins respectively in the first trial after 5 minutes of formalin administration

denoting acute pain. The frequency of paw lick for the mice fed uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet was significantly shorter ($p < 0.05$) than that of the control fed mice. The frequency of paw lick in the uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet fed group was however shorter than in the cooked beans group of mice ($p < 0.05$). In the second trial after 30 minutes of formalin administration denoting chronic pain, the frequency of paw licks was 0.87 ± 0.22 ; 0.57 ± 0.30 ; 0.14 ± 0.14 and 0.14 ± 0.14 /5mins for mice fed normal, cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet respectively. The frequency of right hind paw lick in the uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet fed mice was also significantly shorter ($p < 0.05$) than those of the control fed mice.

Figure 1: Frequency of right hand paw licks recorded of the different experimental groups after two trial during formalin test for assessment of pains.

Values are mean \pm SEM, n = 10.

* $p < 0.05$ vs control;

a = $p < 0.05$ vs cooked beans

Duration of Hind Paw Lick Following Formalin Administration

The values for duration of hind paw lick following administration of normal, cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diets were 26.79 ± 2.56 ; 27.18 ± 4.43 ; 17.75 ± 2.32 and 8.67 ± 2.08 seconds respectively in the first 5 minutes. The duration of hind paw lick in the uncooked beans and serotonin precursor fed mice was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to control. While the uncooked beans group was significantly lower compared to cooked beans group of mice. However, the serotonin precursor fed mice was also significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to cooked and uncooked beans group of mice. In the second trial, after 30 minutes of formalin administration, the hind paw lick duration in the group of mice fed normal, cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diets were 1.30 ± 0.52 ; 0.96 ± 0.51 ; 0.16 ± 0.16 and 0.16 ± 0.16 seconds respectively. The duration of hind paw lick was significantly lower in the uncooked bean and serotonin precursor fed mice compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Duration of right hand paw licks of the different experimental groups after two trial during formalin test for assessment of pains. Values are mean \pm SEM, n = 10.

* $p < 0.05$ vs control;
 a = $p < 0.05$ vs cooked beans;
 b = $p < 0.05$ vs uncooked beans

Frequency of Hind Paw Attention Following Formalin Administration.

The values for the frequency of hind paw attention following administration of normal, cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet were 24.00 ± 2.07 ; 11.43 ± 1.39 ; 8.14 ± 1.18 and $6.00 \pm 0.82/5\text{mins}$ respectively in the first trial after 5 minutes of formalin administration. The frequency of hind paw attention was significantly lower in the cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor fed mice compared to control ($p < 0.05$). However, the serotonin precursor fed mice was also significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to cooked beans group of mice. In the second trial, after 30 minutes of formalin administration, the values were 1.20 ± 0.47 ; 0.57 ± 0.37 ; 0.43 ± 0.30 and 0.43 ± 0.30 . The frequency of hind paw attention was significantly lower in the cooked and uncooked beans group compared to control ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Right hand paw attention frequency of the different experimental groups after two trial during formalin test for assessment of pains.

Values are mean \pm SEM, n = 10.

*significantly different from control at $p < 0.05$

a = $p < 0.05$ vs cooked beans

Duration of Hind Paw Attention Following Formalin Administration.

The values for the duration of hind paw attention following administration of normal, cooked; uncooked beans and serotonin precursor diet were 89.38 ± 11.33 ; 58.64 ± 8.90 ; 53.59 ± 4.14 and 39.03 ± 5.51 seconds respectively. The duration of hind paw attention fed with cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor was statistically shorter than those fed with control diet ($p < 0.05$). In the second trial, after 30 minutes of administration of formalin, the duration of paw attention was 2.60 ± 0.60 ; 0.92 ± 0.71 ; 0.37 ± 0.24 and 0.55 ± 0.39 seconds respectively. The duration of hind paw attention was significantly lower in the cooked, uncooked beans and serotonin precursor fed mice compared to control ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Right hand paw attention duration of the different experimental groups after two trial during formalin test for assessment of pains.

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10.

*significantly different from control at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

This formalin test was in two phases (Ito *et al.*, 2001). The response within the first 30 seconds following formalin injection is the perception of acute pain, while the later period shows chronic pain perception. Frequency of hind paw attention and hind paw-licking following injection with formalin was defined as the number of times the mice lick or shake their hind paw after injection with formalin. Lower frequencies of hind paw attention and hind paw licking indicate analgesic effect while higher frequencies indicate hyperalgesia. The threshold for the perception of pain during the acute and chronic phases was increased in the mice that consumed cooked and uncooked beans diets, but higher in the uncooked beans group when compared to the cooked beans group of mice. This indicates that beans particularly uncooked beans have an analgesic effect in mice. This may be so because beans contain 5-HTP (serotonin precursor) and 5-HT (serotonin) that plays a positive role in the brain analgesia system (Osim, 2008; Sembulingam and Sembulingam, 2010). A second set of experiments implicated the serotonergic pathway, as the threshold for pain perception was increased in the mice that consumed the serotonin precursor diet. The observed higher potency of uncooked beans may be because cooking impairs the serotonin content in the beans.

Conclusion

It is therefore interesting to note that beans diet can be beneficial in the reduction of chronic pain if the results in mice can be extrapolated to man.

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